

Efficient intrusion detection using machine learning techniques

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Abstract

Network attacks in network traffic are vital and well known problems which can subdue the basic security concerns like confidentiality, integrity and availability of both the individuals and enterprise. In this paper, a detailed analysis of the existing intrusion detection systems is done. A Network Based Intrusion Detection System framework with efficient machine learning approach has been proposed. The proposed scheme is simple and also efficient in detecting all the attacks with higher detection accuracy. Results obtained show that the Random Forest machine learning technique outperforms the other machine learning techniques in identifying and classifying attack and normal behavior in a network. An automated security auditing with rule based classifier is also added to confirm if the incorrectly classified data is an attack or normal data. After confirmation of the attack, the alert signal is generated to user as well to network administrator. The proposed system will increase the overall accuracy and also reduce the false alarm rates.

Keywords: *Intrusion detection system, random forest, classifier, attack, accuracy.*

1. Introduction

The word intrusion aims at decreasing the confidentiality, availability and integrity of the entire computer resources or asset [1]. There exist many types of intruders such as masquerader, misfeasor, clandestine users, etc. The attackers and attacks cause threats to network security by means of trespassing by unauthorized users, stealing of assets, acquisition of privileges, performing beyond the limit and injecting malicious activity into the network traffic. In order to solve the above mentioned problems, Intrusion Detection System (IDS) have been developed to assist in monitoring the whole network traffic and to analyze the network traffic as normal or abnormal. IDS can be of both software and hardware mechanisms. The different types of intrusion Detection System (IDS) are discussed in Figure 1. IDS acts as preventive layer of security in detecting known the attacks.

2. Types of IDS

Due to the variations in network configurations several types of intrusion detection types are emerged. Each type of IDS have various advantages and disadvantages in terms of cost, configuration and detection rate. Major use of the intrusion detection system is to analyze/monitor the network traffic and the test whether the traffic is normal or variant. Based on their deployed area, IDS is classified as host based IDS, network based IDS, and hypervisor based IDS and distributed IDS.

Host based IDS

In host based IDS, the intrusive events are detected by collecting the information from a particular host and analyzing with system logs and audit records of the operating system. If there is any variation in the behavior of the system, it is noted to the network manager stating that the network/system is under attack [2]. The major drawback of HIDS is that requirement of storage space for audit logs and history events are more.

Network based IDS

The Network Based IDS captures the entire network traffic and analyzes it, in order to detect if there are any possible intrusions.

Intrusion detection analysis is performed by analyzing the captured Internet Protocol packets and transport layer header of the captured packets. NIDS will use both anomaly and signature based detection techniques [3]. The major drawback is that it cannot analyze encrypted packets and hence cannot detect the attack.

Fig. 1: Types of IDS

Hypervisor based IDS

The communication between the virtual machine in a distributed cloud environment is done with the help of hypervisor. Hypervisor based IDS is the system deployed in the hypervisor layer. It helps in detecting the anomalies between the Virtual Machine and hypervisor.

Distributed IDS

There exist many IDS in Distributed IDS (DIDS). DIDS is deployed in the large scale network in order to detect the anomalies or intrusive behavior of such networks. DIDS has the ability to communicate with the entire distributed server. DIDS includes two major components namely Detection component and correlation manager. DIDS is deployed in the processing sever and also in the host machine.

3. Literature survey

All the networks in recent time are moving towards a completely distributed environment. Therefore vulnerability to attacks and intrusions has increased in an exponential scale. Firewall protects the network from known signatures and unrequired access. It is usually treated as the first line of defense for any network. Firewalls are used to deny or allow protocols, ports or IP addresses. Firewall diverts incoming traffic according to predefined policy. By default, Firewall is deployed in main server or entry point of the network; however a firewall cannot detect the attacks and intrusions to the core because the firewall analyzes only the headers of the packet and not the context or the method of operation. But IDS helps in detecting the attack and intrusions both inside and outside of the network [4].

Machine Learning Algorithms are the emerging techniques that play a vital role in effective Intrusion Detection and Prevention (IDPS). Very Fast Decision Tree algorithm has emerged from the enhancement in Decision Tree is used as the fine coarse grain approach [5]. EDADT algorithm helps in classifying the network traffic effectively and increases the accuracy [6]. Superior detection rate is achieved by Bayesian classifier and it reduces the prompting of False Alarm Rate (FAR) [7]. Neighborhood Outlier Factor (NOF) is used to detect the attack in a specific way to remove the outliers but its lack in efficiency and distance computation provided CPU utilization is also high [8]. Stepwise categorization algorithm including the random forest with other machine learning techniques helps in getting high level accuracy but it includes numerous similar attack behaviors [9]. Decision Forest used as machine learning approach in order to detect the anomalies with density estimation and with manifold learning but it requires high computational overhead this goes similar with conventional Decision Forest learns with Router behavior [10].

Supervised machine learning techniques is significant in detecting the adversities but it requires the rework to make it better in the theme of network security[11]. ML techniques paves an efficient way in detecting the Brute Force attack in the network level by data collecting and data capturing methods using the combined classifiers namely C4.5, 5NN, Naive Bayes[12]. Multi objective feature selection increases the detection accuracy [13]. IDA analyzer software is used in detecting the intrusions in the network traffic and its performed by the rule based classifier however the accuracy.

Artificial Neural Network classifier[14] used in IDS reduces the feature selection by using the concept of information gain and correlation factors but the further extended study is also done to rework in increasing the feature selection in order to increase the efficient accuracy. Feature augmentation with Support Vector Bible proposed the efficient Intrusion Detection with better accuracy with high performance however the time consumption is high[15].

Collaborative Intrusion Detection System comprises of decision Tree and Support Vector Machine along with election clustering algorithm, this includes audit phase, learning phase and detection phase and SNORT is used here to capture the network traffic and performs the signature pattern matching algorithm. This proposed methodology increases the accuracy and detection rate however the unknown attacks are been detected effectively [16].

Stream clustering algorithm along with DBSCAN and Histogram technique comprised together to detect the anomalies in the network traffic but the performance is wavered often [17].

4. Problem statement

Even after many possible solutions, problem exists,

- Due to structural similarities in network traffic dataset, the attack is considered as the normal (High Correlation).
- The basic accuracy and detection rate needs improvement with efficient performance.

5. Proposed frame work

In this section, the proposed framework on efficient intrusion detection using the Robust Fast Machine Learning approach is described. The proposed system has two phases such as training phase and testing phase. In automated security systems, it is important to make the machine/system to learn the process and pursue the work in the automated way. Many machine learning and finite sate machine learning tools and studies are emerging in recent days. Major research work is going on to find the best and robust Machine Learning techniques to work with.

In the proposed system NSL-KDD dataset is being used to do the further step of learning process [18]. The sub phases are data preprocessing, feature section and classification.

Data Preprocessing

Real world data is often lacking in certain behavior/trends, inconsistent and incomplete data. Data preprocessing is known to be a well-known proven method to sort out this issues. Here data preprocessing is consider to be as a data mining technique which helps in

transforming raw data into understandable format. In Weka data preprocessing includes the process of data cleaning, data transformation, data integration and it also avoids redundant and truncated data. Quality decisions are always based on the quality data set. With the help of data preprocessing the data quality can be measured in terms of consistency, completeness, believability and accuracy [19].

- Data Cleaning: Real world data is often subjected as dirt data. It includes the missing values and duplication of records. These problems can be clarified by ignoring a particular tuple which has the missing values and it's done manually or even with machine inspection.
- Data Integration: In real case scenario network traffic can be obtained from various data sources. This network data can be combined with the original dataset for further analysis. But the major problem created by data integration is redundancy and schema integration.
- Data Transformation: This process helps in Finally the classifier classifies whether the attack is normal or attack transforming the real world network traffic into weka KDD Dataset Real Dataset are smoothing, normalization and aggregation.
- Data Reduction: It can be done through data cube aggregation, data compression and concept hierarchy generation. This solves the time consumption in analyzing the huge amount of dataset.

The proposed framework is shown in Fig.2. The training and other processes are performed using weka tool, which has the built in process to extract the network traffic information. Which includes the IP source address, destination address, flag, services based on protocol, host bytes etc. Each single record consists of set of features. In NSL-KDD dataset consists of 41 features (Attributes). The main work of data preprocessing is to deal with Scalar transformation, avoiding Null Values/labels, and setting a default number for empty data. Each record consists of two classes they are attack or normal.

Feature selection

In NSL-KDD dataset, it consists of 41 attributes. This feature selection is the main thing required in the classification process. In weka, attributes can be chosen manually by knowing the outcome of the classifier the feature selection can be modified accordingly, some of the features includes are Basic features, content features, network features and host features[6].

Classification

- After data preprocessing, the data is subjected to build training and testing model [20]. This mainly helps in describing and distinguishing the data classes and concept. Data classification has includes two process
- Training Dataset: Pre-Classification is required in every object.
- Testing Dataset: with the created model by the preceding step is tested by assigning class labels to data objects in a test dataset.
- The created model is given as the input for machine learning classification algorithm. Classification phase does the process of classifying the records in the dataset into attack or normal data. In the first process of training dataset is given as the input to the selected robust fast machine learning algorithm with the answer known. Based on the learning algorithm the IDS model classifies the each record data and present the output.
- Then the 20% of the testing dataset is given as the input for learning algorithm with answer unknown. Testing dataset also undergoes the preprocessing phase to eliminate the outliers or other false alarm detections. By doing this each record gets ready for classification without any missing values.
- Finally the classifier classifies whether the attack is normal or attack.

Fig. 2: Architecture of the proposed system

6. Methodology used in the proposed framework

Random Forest is supervised machine learning algorithm used for classification and regression (mean predictions). It is considered to be as the ensemble machine learning algorithm included with bootstrap aggregation and bagging. Bootstrap aggregation mainly helps in building multiple models from a single training dataset. This also further leads to some fine adjustment to bagging and results in very powerful classifier. Random forest helps in solving predictive modeling problems like understanding

attack or normal network traffic. Random Forest works with stoholic discrimination or stoholic guessing. This totally depends with probability. Bootstrap aggregation has less variance where high variance is present in CART (Decision Tree). Random forest works by generating numerous sub trees and the results predicted by the algorithm has less correlation [21]. As mentioned earlier, decision tree like CART model choose a variable and split takes place based on the greedy algorithm this minimizes the error. Even with bagging it undergoes structural similarities and ends up in high correlation in their predictions.

Fig. 3: Steps in Random Forest

The After classifying the network traffic into attack or normal, the normal network data is send to the authorized network and attack data undergoes the following steps; For the further confirmation of the attack, the attack network traffic is passed to automated security auditing. Where the automated security auditing comprises the rule based classifier, provided with set of predefined rules which are listed below; after the confirmation of attack by the rule based classifier it generates the alarm signals and sends to user as well to cloud service provider. Finally it also stores the attack data in the database for further use.

7. Performance metrics

In order to build a highly efficient Intrusion Detection System (IDS), things involved are accuracy, detection rate, precision, recall, F-measure, Sensitivity. These metrics helps in increase the detection rate and reduce false alarm rate [19].

- Accuracy:** Highlight Accuracy is termed to find how intrusion detection system is detecting the normal and attack network traffic. Accuracy is also called as Classification Rate.

$$CR = \frac{\text{True Negative} + \text{True Positive}}{\text{True Negative} + \text{False Positive} + \text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}}$$
- Detection Rate:** In IDS Sensitivity/Detection Rate/True Positive Rate is defined as the propotion of the normal behaviour in the network traffic. Correctly detected anomalus: Total number of anomalus in the network.

$$\text{Detection Rate} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}}$$
- False Positive Rate (FPR):** When the normal networktraffic is considered as attack. The IDS generates alert incorrectly. similarities are also been detected with help of Random Forest algorithm.

$$FPR = \frac{\text{False Positive}}{\text{Number of negatives}}$$
- False Negative Rate(FNR):** When the anomalus/attack network traffic is considered normal probaly IDS doesnt generate alert as an output.

$$FNR = \frac{\text{False Negative}}{\text{Number of Negatives}}$$
- True Negative Rate/Specificity:** Specificity value is 1 if no anomaly is present, but it is unusal in IDS.

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{\text{True Negative}}{\text{TrueNegative} + \text{False Positive}}$$

8. Result discussion

Comparing NSL-KDD dataset with other machine learning algorithms

The dataset with 41 attributes is compared with other machine learning algorithm such as naive Bayes, Decision tree etc., but the SVM and Random Forest has the same accuracy. Therefore the final comparison is made between SVM and random forest. This comparison of result analysis is made for the entire dataset, training dataset (20%) and testing dataset are listed below in Tables. The overall accuracy of Random forest and SVM are same but the time taken to build the model and time taken to build the test model is different. Random Forest machine learning algorithm has the low time consumption compared with SVM specified in Table 1, 2, 3. Also the NSL-KDD dataset is given as the input to various machine learning algorithms but Random Forest algorithm holds the higher detection rate with increased accuracy. Structural similarities are also been detected with help of Random Forest algorithm.

- Whole Dataset
- Instances- 125973

Table 1: Evaluation of NSL KDD dataset (Whole Dataset)

Machine learning algorithm	Model building Time (sec)	Time taken to build test model	Correctly classified instances	Incorrectly classified instances
Random Forest	209.85	11.4	125966	7
SVM	0.04	3504.95	125966	7

- Training Dataset 20%
- Instances—25192

Table 2: Evaluation of NSL KDD dataset (Training Dataset 20%)

Machine learning algorithm	Model building Time (sec)	Time taken to build test model	Correctly classified instances	Incorrectly classified instances
Random Forest	30.8	3.23	25191	1
SVM	0.02	169.45	25191	1

- Testing Dataset
- Instances-22544

Table 3: Evaluation of NSL KDD dataset (Testing Dataset)

Machine learning algorithm	Model building Time (sec)	Time taken to build test model	Correctly classified instances	Incorrectly classified instances
Random Forest	0.46	0.24	22490	54
SVM	0.01	108.48	22490	54

Table 1, 2 and 3 concludes that in Intrusion Detection System, evaluation of NSL-KDD dataset with both random forest and SVM machine learning approach provides the similar overall accuracy. But the time taken to build the training model and test the model in SVM takes high time consumption compared to Random Forest.

9. Conclusion

In this paper, the proposed IDS uses random forest machine learning technique for network based Intrusion Detection System in classifying the normal and abnormal activities in the network. The NSL-KDD dataset is used since it is publically available with pruned features. Results from the proposed model demonstrate that the classification algorithm with data preprocessing and feature selection can achieve 99% of accuracy. However, with higher detection accuracy, categorization accuracy is relatively lower because of the structural similarity in the network traffic behaviors. Therefore proposed a framework with automated security auditing inclined with rule based classifier will be able to detect the similar network traffic behavior and increase the overall accuracy with higher classification of the dataset. Also after confirming the attack, the alert signal is generated for user and cloud service provider. The real time attack data is stored in the database for the further use. This framework can also be applied to cloud environments to increase the security of the network.

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